

Eu³⁺ PHOTOLUMINESCENCE IN MONONUCLEAR COORDINATION COMPOUNDS WITH DIFFERENT LIGANDS

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(Received October 18, 2018)

Abstract

Novel Eu³⁺-based photoluminescent (PL) organic coordination compounds have been synthesized; their optical properties in the UV–Vis spectrum have been characterized. The paper presents results of studying mononuclear coordination compounds (MCCs) with the Eu³⁺ ion, namely, Eu(*o*-MBA)₃Phen, Eu(TTA)₃(Ph₃PO)₂, Eu(DBM)₃Phen, and Eu(DBM)₃(Ph₃PO)₁H₂O. The energy of the absorption threshold (E_g) for all the studied ligands has been found to be greater than the energy required for excitation of the ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_0$ transitions within the transitions $4f$ orbital of the Eu³⁺ ion. The PL emission spectra of the studied coordination compounds are associated with the internal transitions of the Eu³⁺: ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_i$ ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$). Emission peak positions in the PL spectra are registered around 537, 580, 612, 650, and 702 nm. The FWHM of the dominant PL band at 612 nm is less than 10 nm; this finding indicates that MCCs exhibit atomic-like fluorescence emission and color purity.

1. Introduction

Coordination compounds of rare earth elements (REEs) are excellent materials for various applications because of a number of their specific properties: high efficiency (100% theoretical efficiency), easy color tuneability, temperature insensitivity, chemical environmental stability, etc. [1]. These properties enable them to be applied in various fields of optoelectronics and monochromatic light sources for organic light emitting diodes [2], luminescent sensors [2], waveguide amplifiers [3], etc. An important domain for application of coordination compounds is related to medicine and biology for tissue and cell imaging [4], drug delivery monitoring, etc [5].

Direct excitation of Eu³⁺ ions and their luminescence are negligible because the cross section of the REE ions related to absorption of the excitation light is small. Their luminescence can be significantly improved, if the REE ions are coordinated to the organic ligands with high absorption of light and form complex compounds of REEs. Enhancement of the fluorescence intensity in these compounds is associated with the energy transfer from organic ligands to REE ions.

The $4f$ orbital of the Eu³⁺ ion is shielded by electrons with a higher energy on the $5s^2$ and $5p^6$ orbital levels. This feature is responsible for an insignificant effect of the outer compound environment and crystalline symmetry on the $4f \rightarrow 4f$ transitions in of the Eu³⁺ ion. A way to overcome the problem of poor absorption of europium ions and to achieve high photoluminescence (PL) emissions is to surround the REE ion with compatible organic ligands

that are capable of absorbing the excitation light and transferring the absorbed energy to $4f$ states of the REE ion. At the same time, the surrounding ligands offer a rigid coordination protection to minimize nonradiative losses of luminescence. The saturation of the Eu^{3+} coordinate sphere with ligands allows the ion to be protected from the action of water molecules or other media that can stop luminescence [4].

Ligands play the role of complexation agents for mononuclear coordination compounds (MCCs). They can be divided into ionic ligands with chemical valence bonds and anionic neutral coordinating ligands (Table 1). The proper choice of ligands is very important for improving the luminescence efficiency of coordination compounds with Eu^{3+} ions. This is why the choice of ligands in a mononuclear compounds and their coordination with the Eu^{3+} ion is a problem that should be further studied.

This study is focused on two aims: first, to study the optical properties of various ligands to provide their optimum selection for synthesizing new MCCs and, second, to develop methods for the synthesis of new organic coordination compounds $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_1\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3\text{Phen}$, $\text{Eu}(o\text{-MBA})_3\text{Phen}$, and $\text{Eu}(\text{TTA})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_2$ and study their luminescent properties.

2. Methodology

2.1 Experimental

The physical properties of coordination compounds were characterized by UV-Vis and IR spectroscopy. Optical transmission spectra were measured in a spectral range of 300–800 nm on a SPECORD UV-Vis instrument (Carl Zeiss Jena). The PL of high-resolution emission spectra of powder samples were recorded using different excitation light sources: a 5-mW nitrogen laser at 337 nm at a repetition rate of 10–100 Hz and a LD source at 405 nm. The PL signal was detected using a Hamamatsu H8259-01 photomultiplier module and a C8855-01 counting unit connected to a PC. Fluorescence measurements were performed in a photon counting mode. The spectral resolution for PL spectra measurements was as low as 0.25 nm. The time-resolved PL intensity decays were recorded using an N_2 pulsed laser with a pulse width of 10 ns at a repetition rate of 10 Hz. The time resolution of the set-up was 50 μs , which was sufficient for the registration of the kinetics of the PL relaxation in a range of up to 10 ms. All PL spectra were measured at room temperature.

2.2. Technological Details and Ligand Characterization

To study the PL properties of Eu^{3+} MCCs, the following set of MCCs was designed and synthesized: $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3\text{Phen}$, $\text{Eu}(o\text{-MBA})_3\text{Phen}$, $\text{Eu}(\text{TTA})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_2$, and $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_1\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The ligands selected for synthesis of the MCCs are optimal for controlling the luminescence properties by the energy transfer mechanism and improving the compatibility and dissolution in various solvents. The chemical structures of the ligands are shown in Fig. 1. The ligands were applied as complexation agents for MCCs based on the Eu^{3+} ion. Both ionic ligands with valence chemical bonds and anionic coordination ligands were used.

The ligands were used to prepare REE coordination compounds and provide effective transitions of energy to the central Eu^{3+} ion. From the ligands absorption spectra, the absorption thresholds of the studied ligands were determined: thenoyltrifluoroacetone (TTA), α,α dipy, dibenzoylmethane (DBM), Dipic, Phen, triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO), *o*-methylbenzoic acid

(*o*-MBA), and methanol (see Table 1).

All reagents used for the preparation of the Eu^{3+} coordination compounds were of analytical grade (~99.5% purity, Sigma Aldrich) and used without further purification. The ligands are divided into two groups: (1) ligands with valence anionic–cationic bonds, namely, TTA, DBM, and *o*-MBA and (2) ligands with coordinating bonds to the Eu^{3+} ion, namely, Phen and Ph_3PO . Both types of ligands are used as complexation agents of MCCs and as key components for absorption of excitation light and subsequent energy transfer to the central Eu^{3+} ion. In addition to providing technological compatibility with different solvents, ligands ensure electrons transition to the 5D_0 level of the Eu^{3+} ion with subsequent $^5D_0 \rightarrow ^7F_j$ transitions within the $4f$ shell.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of ligands used for the preparation of organic coordination compounds: (a) Phen, (b) Ph_3PO , (c) *o*-MBA, (d) TTA, and (e) DBM.

Table 1. Absorption threshold of ligands

Ligand	Ligand type	E_g , eV
TTA	ionic	3.06
α,α dipy	anionic	3.4
DBM	ionic	3.11
Dipic	anionic	3.25
Phen	anionic	3.56
Ph_3PO	anionic	3.72
<i>o</i> -MBA	ionic	4.15
methanol	solvent	3.21; 3.23; 4.25

2.3. Synthesis of Eu^{3+} -Based Coordination Compounds

Eu(DBM)₃Phen–tris(1,3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione)1,10-phenanthroline Europium(III)

In this case, 0.67 g of DBM was dissolved in 10 mL of ethanol (96%); 0.2 g of phenanthroline was added to this solution; the resulting mixture was a light yellow transparent solution. Three milliliters of a 1 N NaOH solution were added to the resulting solution. The color became intense yellow. After that, 0.26 g of the EuCl_3 salt was added to 5 mL of ethanol. An incomplete dissolution was observed, and turbidity remained. Upon addition of 1 mL of H_2O , the material was completely dissolved; however, the turbidity remained.

The saturated solution was admixed with a few droplets of a EuCl_3 solution; a yellow viscous compound immediately precipitated. Subsequently, it was dissolved, filtered, and washed with ethanol and chloroform. As a result, after filtration and drying, 0.55 g of the material was dissolved in acetone. From analytical calculations for $\text{C}_{57}\text{H}_{41}\text{EuN}_2\text{O}_6$, the following content was determined (%): C, 68.33; H, 4.13; and N, 2.80. From elemental analysis, it was found (%): C, 68.43; H, 4.28; and N, 2.29.

Eu(o-MBA)₃Phen–tris(2-methylbenzoic acid)1,10-phenanthroline Europium(III)

Warmed ethanol (96%) with 0.4 g (3 mmol) of *o*-methylbenzoic acid and 0.2 g (1 mmol) of 1,10-phenanthroline were adjusted to a pH value of 6.0–7.0 with a 1 M NaOH solution. Further, europium chloride (1 mmol) was dissolved in 5 mL of water, added dropwise to the organic mixture, and stirred. A light pink precipitate was formed immediately. The precipitate was filtered, washed with small portions of ethanol, and dried thoroughly in air. The synthesis yield was 0.56 g (37.6%). From analytical calculations for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$, it was found (%): Eu, 20.61; C, 58.63; H, 3.97; and N, 3.80. From elemental analysis, it was found (%): Eu, 20.88; C, 59.23; H, 4.17; and N, 3.75.

Eu(TTA)₃(Ph₃PO)₂–tris(4,4,4-trifluoro-1-(2-thienyl)-1,3-butanedione bis(phenyl- λ -phosphine oxide)Europium(III)

In this case, 0.66 g (3 mmol) of TTA and 0.56 g (2 mmol) of TPPO were dissolved in 10 mL of warm 96% ethanol, and 3 mL of a 1 N sodium hydroxide solution was added. The mixture was stirred, while 1 mmol of europium chloride in 5 mL of water was added dropwise. A light pink precipitate was immediately formed. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with small portions of ethanol and diethyl ether, and dried thoroughly in air; the solid of the complex was obtained. The yield was 0.68 g. From analytical calculations for $\text{C}_{60}\text{H}_{42}\text{F}_9\text{EuO}_8\text{P}_2\text{S}_3$, it was found (%): C, 52.53; H, 3.09. From elemental analysis, it was found (%): C, 52.37 and 52.28; H, 3.18 and 2.98.

Eu(DBM)₃(Ph₃PO)₁H₂O–tris(1,3-phenyl-1,3-propanedione) mono(phenyl- λ -phosphine oxide) aqua Europium(III)

In this case, 0.5 g (2.24 mmol) of DBM and 0.21 g of TPPO (0.746 mmol) were dissolved in 10 mL of heated 96% ethanol to the resulting warm solution. A filtered solution of 0.19 g (0.746 mmol) of europium chloride hexahydrate was dissolved in a mixture of 2 mL of

water and 1 mL of ethanol, and 2.3 mL of 1 N sodium hydroxide solution were added. During mixing and grinding, a creamy residue precipitated. The resulting precipitate was washed with water and then with methanol and ether. The substance is readily soluble in methanol and ether. The yield was 0.42 g. Analysis for chlorine negative, analysis for europium: analytical calculations (%): 13.59. From elemental analysis, it was found (%): 13.81.

3. Optical and Luminescence Characterization of the MCCs

3.1. Optical Properties of the MCCs

Absorption spectra $\alpha(\lambda)$ of the solutions with the different ligands and for the different MCCs in the UV–Vis domain show absorption bands with the first sharp absorption threshold in the spectral range of 330–380 nm. These bands are apparently attributed to the absorption of the coordinating ionic ligands incorporated in the organic compound.

The absorption thresholds of the ligands and MCCs were determined from the Tauc plot $(ah\nu)^{1/n} = f(h\nu)$, where the value of exponent n is determined by the nature of the amorphous–crystalline material transition: for allowed direct transitions, $n = 1/2$ [5]. From linear interpolation of the experimental plot, we obtained the energy values for the absorption threshold $E_g = \text{LOMO} - \text{HOMO}$ (where HOMO is the energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital, and LUMO is the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital). In this way, from experimental data, energy values E_g were estimated for each ligand: $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_1\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.83 eV; $\text{Eu}(\text{TTA})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_2$, 3.05 eV; $\text{Eu}(o\text{-MBA})_3\text{Phen}$, 3.42 eV; and $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3\text{Phen}$, 3.11 eV.

3.2. Luminescent Properties of the MCCs

The PL spectra of all coordinating compounds with the Eu^{3+} ions have similar shapes and almost identical emission peaks. The only difference between them is the maximum magnitude of the PL intensity that determines the efficacy (Table 2). The radiative transitions of europium ions can be observed in PL spectra; they are centered at around 580, 590, 612–615, 651, and 700 nm (Figs. 4a–4d). These emission bands are attributed to internal $4f$ electron transitions ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_i$ ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$) of the Eu^{3+} ion with a dominant emission band in the region of 612–615 nm (${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$). Comparison of the PL spectra of the studied MCCs shows an increase in the PL intensity in $\text{Eu}(\text{TTA})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_2$ by about 4.6 times in comparison with the intensity of the other studied MCCs.

The high efficiency of PL in coordinating compounds with Eu^{3+} ions is attributed to the mechanism of energy transfer through the excited electrons states from the singlet (S) and triplet (T) levels of the ligands to the central Eu^{3+} ion (Fig. 5). The observed emission bands are associated with radiative transitions ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_i$ from the excited states in the Eu^{3+} $4f$ shell. It was found that, of all the studied compounds, $\text{Eu}(\text{TTA})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_2$ exhibits the most efficient energy transfer from ligands to the Eu^{3+} ion (Fig. 4a).

From analysis of the experimental results on PL and absorption spectra, we can identify a cascade of the energy transfer from the LUMO energy levels of ligands to the energetic levels of the $4f$ electronic shell of the Eu^{3+} ion. It should be noted that the energy of the S and T levels of ligands in MCCs is higher than the energies of the respective PL bands of the Eu^{3+} ion ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_j$ (Fig. 6).

4. Discussion

4.1. Energy Transfer

Energy transfer through the excitation of electrons takes place between different sites within the same molecule (intramolecular transfer). In the case of the radiation mechanism, known as the Förster's mechanism of energy transfer [6], the acceptor (Eu^{3+} ion) receives absorbed energy of the donor (ligands) in form of photons (Figs. 5, 6).

The transfer of radiative energy takes place when the energy of the electron excitation of the acceptor is greater than that of the donor. This process is fast enough to take place over the lifetime of the excited state.

The energy transfer mechanism in the Förster process is illustrated by the scheme shown in Fig. 5:

where L and L^* denotes the unexcited and excited ligands, respectively; hv_0 is the excitation photon energy; hv_1 is the ligand emission photon energy; hv_2 is the emission photon energy from the Eu^{3+} ion; and Eu^{3+*} denotes the Eu^{3+} ion in the excited state.

The efficiency of the energy transfer process depends on the spectral overlap between the ligand emission and the absorbance of the Eu^{3+} acceptor.

The Dexter energy transfer process is an electron exchange mechanism [7]. The Dexter mechanism takes place between the ligand and the Eu^{3+} ion, which are extremely close and, in most cases, molecularly connected. This mechanism is also referred to as the electronic mechanism carried out by molecular chemical bonds. Energy transfer is the process by which an excited triplet or singlet state of the ligand creates an excited state in the Eu^{3+} ion. The Dexter relation below illustrates the overall form of the electron exchange mechanism (Fig. 5):

where e^* denotes the excited electron.

The distance separating the ligand and acceptor sites of Eu^{3+} is fairly small and facilitates an efficient energy transfer due to the minimum spacing within the MCC molecule.

The energy levels of the emitting states 5D_i of Eu^{3+} are smaller than the threshold energy obtained from extinction coefficient (ϵ) for the mentioned ligands. The electronic state with the lowest energy value of the ligand in the triplet state is greater than that of the lowest transition ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$; therefore, the expected energy transfer occurs. To provide an efficient energy transfer, the triplet energy of the ligand should be greater than or equal to the europium level of 5D_0 (${}^5D_0 = 17264 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The identification of the PL bands in the spectrum in Fig. 2c is characteristic of transitions of excited electrons from the 5D_0 level to 7F_i . This also refers to the spectra shown in Figs. 2a, 2b, and 2d.

The dominant emission band associated with the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$ optical transition can be deconvoluted into three to five bands (Fig. 3). According to Judd–Ofelt theory [4, 11, 2], it can be speculated that the studied compounds have a triclinic symmetry of the lattice.

Fig. 2. PL spectra and chemical structure of Eu³⁺ MCCs: (a) Eu(o-MBA)₃phen, (b) Eu(DBM)₃phen, (c) Eu(DBM)₃(Ph₃PO)₁H₂O, and (d) Eu(TTA)₃(Ph₃PO)₂. The excitation wavelength is 337 nm.

Fig. 3. PL spectra and their deconvolution (in green) of MCCs for the luminescent band associated with the ⁵D₀ → ⁷F₂ transition (in Fig. 2) of Eu(DBM)₃(Ph₃PO)₁H₂O and Eu(DBM)₃phen; λ_{exc} = 337 nm.

Figure 4 illustrates the decay of PL intensity under pulsed laser excitation plotted in the $\ln(I_{\text{PL}})-t$ coordinates. The exponential pattern of the decay, as in Fig. 4, is characteristic of all the MCCs studied here. This plot corresponds to the exponential decay of the PL intensity, which can be described by the following relation: $I = I_0 \cdot \exp(-t/\tau)$, where τ is the characteristic time of the spontaneous PL decay. For the MCCs, the τ values are listed in Table 2.

The interpretation of the PL spectra is made in terms of the Judd–Ofelt theory [8, 9]. The estimated values of the transition probabilities and efficiency of PL were calculated (Table 2). The intensity of emission transitions are described by the relation

$$I_{0 \rightarrow j} = h\nu_{0 \rightarrow j} A_{0 \rightarrow j} N_0, \quad (3)$$

where $h\nu_{0 \rightarrow j}$ is the energy maximum of the transition, N_0 is the concentration of the emitting centers of Eu^{3+} ions, and $A_{0 \rightarrow j}$ is the Einstein coefficients of spontaneous emission. The coefficients of spontaneous emission $A_{0 \rightarrow j}$ are obtained from the equation

$$A_{0 \rightarrow j} = \frac{\lambda_{0 \rightarrow j} \times I_{0 \rightarrow j}}{\lambda_{0 \rightarrow 1} \times I_{0 \rightarrow 1}} \times A_{0 \rightarrow 1}, \quad (4)$$

where $I_{0 \rightarrow j}$ corresponds to the integrated PL intensity related to the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_j$ transition, and $\lambda_{0 \rightarrow j}$ is the wavelength of the PL maximum of the $0 \rightarrow j$ transitions. For experimental determination of emission coefficients $A_{0 \rightarrow j}$ from the emission spectra, the magnetic dipole, the allowed ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$ transition was used, which is formally insensitive to the chemical environment around the Eu^{3+} ion and, consequently, can be used as a reference $A({}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1) = 50 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [10].

The results of the study of the PL spectra and the calculations performed according to formulas (2)–(4) are shown in Table 2. The PL parameters are as follows: integrated PL intensity (I), λ_{max} , I_{max} , and the probability of $A_{0 \rightarrow j}$ transitions at excitation with a laser beam of 337 or 405 nm. The relaxation time of PL of the MCCs is 0.27 ms for $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_1\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.52 ms for $\text{Eu}(o\text{-MBA})_3\text{Phen}$ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Kinetics of the PL decay after 10-ns pulsed excitation at 337 nm: (a) $\text{Eu}(\text{DBM})_3(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_1\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (b) $\text{Eu}(o\text{-MBA})_3\text{Phen}$.

Table 2. Parameters of PL transitions ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_j$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$) for Eu^{3+} -based MCCs

Eu(<i>o</i> -MBA) ₃ Phen, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 337$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	57.7	1008.3	8412.5	79.1	886.6
λ_{max} , nm	579.4	591.4	615.6	649.7	694.6
I_{max} , quant/s	79.5	167.9	1232.8	40.8	82.1
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	2.8	50	434.1	4.3	51.6
Eu(DBM) ₃ Phen, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 337$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	56.3	156.5	3142	44.3	85.6
λ_{max} , nm	579.5	591.8	611.1	651.5	704.02
I_{max} , quant/s	165.9	91.7	1770.8	64.5	68.2
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	17.6	50	1036.6	15.6	32.5
$\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	168.1	516.7	10088.7	167.3	281.2
λ_{max} , nm	579.2	591.8	611.06	650.6	703.8
I_{max} , quant/s	165.9	91.7	1770.8	64.5	68.2
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	15.9	50	1007.8	17.8	32.3
Eu(TTA) ₃ (Ph ₃ PO) ₂ , $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 337$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	217.3	1677.4	14631.6	260.1	1197.5
λ_{max} , nm	578.5	590.8	613.7	649.4	699.5
I_{max} , quant/s	173.8	276.03	1640.9	111.1	189.1
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	6.3	50	453.02	8.5	42.2
$\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405$ nm (powder)					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	249.7	7677.75	141294.5	2094.3	5557.7
λ_{max} , nm	578.4	588.08	613.5	650.6	692.4
I_{max} , quant/s	478.4	1219.1	22735.8	660.3	769.2
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	1.5	50	960	15.08	42.6
Eu(DBM) ₃ (Ph ₃ PO) ₁ H ₂ O, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 337$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.	57.3	167.9	1716.01	42.2	71.9
λ_{max} , nm	578.8	591.00	611.2	651.8	703.1
I_{max} , quant/s	57.3	53.6	325	40.4	43.6
$A_{0 \rightarrow j}$, s^{-1}	10.04	50	528.2	13.8	25.4
$\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405$ nm					
	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$	${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_4$
<i>I</i> (integrated PL intensity), rel. un.			23.034×10^8	0.3981×10^8	0.2440×10^8
λ_{max} , nm		587.6	610.04	656.6	700.3
I_{max} , quant/s		0.153×10^8	3.2978×10^8	0.0759×10^8	0.0556×10^8

4. Conclusions

A new Eu(DBM)₃(Ph₃PO)₁H₂O PL compound has been synthesized; novel technological schemes for the preparation of Eu(*o*-MBA)₃Phen, Eu(DBM)₃Phen, and Eu(TTA)₃(Ph₃PO)₂ compounds with chosen ligands have been proposed. The MCCs have been characterized by measuring the PL spectral characteristics and the luminescence relaxation kinetics.

The optical properties of a number of ligands have been studied for optimization of the composition in the synthesis of Eu^{3+} -based coordination compounds. The absorption thresholds of both the ligands and the coordinating compounds have been determined. For the studied MCCs, a number of parameters have been determined, namely, absorption threshold, PL transitions

$^5D_0 \rightarrow ^7F_j$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$), PL integrated intensity, PL probability, and relaxation time.

A model of an energy transfer scheme for the Eu^{3+} ion under UV light excitation has been proposed.

Fig. 5. Illustration of the energy transfer mechanism from ligands to the Eu^{3+} ion.

Fig. 6. Positions of energy levels for the absorption threshold of the ligands used in the synthesis of coordination compounds and the levels of the $5D_0 \rightarrow 7F_0$ energy transition of the Eu^{3+} ion.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Institute of Applied Physics (project nos. 11.817.05.03A and 11.817.05.04A) and the Science and Technology Center in Ukraine (project no. 6117). I would like to thank Dr. I. Culeac for PL measurements, Dr. V. Zubareva for the synthesis of Eu^{3+} MCCs, and Prof. M. Iovu and Dr. V. Verlan for discussion of the results.

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